

PHENYLTHIOCARBAMIDES. A CONTRIBUTION TO THE STUDY OF THE TRIAD -N-C-S. PART XVI. THE SUPPOSED FORMATION OF DISULPHIDES BY THE OXIDATION OF THIOCARBAMIDES

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Evidence is adduced to controvert the general belief that unstable disulphides of the formamidine type are the first products of oxidation.

It has been suggested from time to time (for references *vide* this journal, 1944, 21, 17) that in the oxidation of thiocarbamides to thiodiazoles, disulphides are formed as unstable intermediate products but we are not aware of any direct experimental evidence in support of this supposition.

We have already shown (*loc. cit.*) that, contrary to the observation of Dost, a methylphenylthiocarbamide forms an aminobenzthiazole derivative by the action of sulphur monochloride in chloroform, and not a disulphide or a hydrazodithiocarbonamide.

This agrees with the observations of Hofmann and Gabriel (*Ber.*, 1892, 25, 1578) and of De and Chakravarty (*J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1928, 5, 661) who oxidised the same thiocarbamide with iodine or hydrogen peroxide and obtained a thiazole, but does not agree with Lal and Krall (*ibid.*, 1937, 14, 478) who claimed to have obtained methylphenylformamidine disulphide by the action of nitrous acid.

We have therefore re-examined their picrate, finding it to be the picrate of Hofmann and Gabriel's thiodiazole, and we have also isolated the thiodiazole itself. We find no indication of disulphide formation.

We have also oxidised phenylthiocarbamide with nitrous acid in a strong acid medium in the presence of picric acid, when any disulphide formed, even as an intermediate product, should be picked up by the picric acid, but the picrate of Hector's base alone was obtained. This confirms the view of Lal and Krall (*ibid.*, 1939, 16, 31) that Hector's base is a primary product, and is not produced *via* a disulphide.

Fromm (*Annalen*, 1915, 394, 284) working with compounds which were expected to give dithioformamidines came to the similar conclusion that Hegershoff's diazothiol (*Ber.*, 1903, 36, 3130) is formed from *s*-diphenylthiocarbamide directly and not through a disulphide.

Lal and Krall (*J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1938, 15, 217) obtained no disulphide by the action of nitrous acid on *s*-methylphenylthiocarbamide but, under all conditions directly obtained a base probably a thiodiazole $C_{11}H_{11}N_4S$ (they give $C_{12}H_{12}N_4S$).

Vidya Sagar and Krall (*ibid.*, 1940, 17, 475) studied the closely related thiobenzamide but found no evidence of disulphide formation under any conditions.

We conclude, therefore, that aryl thiocarbamides do not yield disulphides on oxidation.

EXPERIMENTAL

Expt. I.—Oxidation of α -methylphenylthiocarbamide with nitrous acid in 1:1 ratio of the reactants in a normal hydrochloric acid medium.—Methylphenylthiocarbamide (8.3 g., 1/20th mole) was dissolved in 200 c.c. of 50% alcohol. 100 c.c. of 4*N*-hydrochloric acid were added to this. An aqueous solution of sodium nitrite containing 3.5 g.

(1/10th mole) in 100 c.c. of water was then gradually run into the thiocarbamide solution during the course of $\frac{1}{2}$ hour. The mixture was constantly stirred. During the earlier stages of the reaction a red colouration developed which eventually faded away. The mixture was allowed to stand for about 1 hour to complete the reaction. A little amorphous yellow solid matter separated out which was filtered and the filtrate examined as follows :—

- (i) A part of the clear filtrate was treated with an excess of aqueous picric acid. A crystalline yellow precipitate separated out which on crystallisation from methyl alcohol melted at $142-43^{\circ}$.
- (ii) A portion of the filtrate was made alkaline with ammonia and extracted with ether. The ethereal extract on evaporation left (a) crystals of sulphur, (b) colourless crystals of m.p. $93-94^{\circ}$, (c) a viscous brown liquid which on standing for over a week deposited crystalline plates of the unreacted thiocarbamide. The crystalline compound of the m.p. $93-94^{\circ}$ gave a yellow picrate (m.p. 142°) with picric acid, its identity with the picrate obtained in (i) above was established by a mixed m.p.

Expt. 2.—Hofmann and Gabriel's thiodiazole was prepared by Chakravarty's method using hydrogen peroxide as the oxidising agent, m.p. $94-95^{\circ}$. It also gave a picrate of m.p. 142° identical with the picrate described in Expt. 1. Further it was found that on treatment with excess of alkali thiodiazole could be recovered from the picrate of Expt. 1 (i).

Expt. 3.—*Oxidation of phenylthiocarbamide with nitrous acid in presence of picric acid.*—Phenylthiocarbamide (1.5 g.) was dissolved in about 100 c.c. of warm aqueous picric acid solution containing about 5 c.c. of concentrated hydrochloric acid. Sodium nitrite (0.7 g.) dissolved in a little water was gradually added. A voluminous yellow precipitate was immediately formed. No other product could be isolated. Crystals from dilute alcohol melt at 203° (mixed m.p. with the picrate from Hector's base).